

Advancing Clinical and Environmental Monitoring: Graphene-Enhanced Bioreceptor Integration

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Our research leverages the exceptional properties of graphene-based nanomaterials and bioreceptors to develop advanced clinical point-of-care and environmental monitoring devices. We focus on fabricating nanostructured three-electrode electrochemical cells using an environmentally friendly, cost-effective, one-step printing/stamping technique [1]. This method employs an infrared laser to simultaneously fabricate highly exfoliated reduced graphene oxide (rGO) decorated with gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) through instantaneous laser-induced co-reduction of graphene oxide (GO) and gold cations (Au³⁺). These structures can be transferred onto flexible supports such as PET or nitrocellulose and combined with other printing method to form the three-electrode system. Functionalising the working electrode surface with DNA-based probes, aptamers, antibodies [2], or nanobodies via various chemical approaches allows for the specific capture and detection of target nucleic acids, proteins, or small molecules. The inclusion of AuNPs on the rGO surface enhances the electrochemical performance by creating multiple active sites, thereby increasing sensitivity for biosensor applications. The bio-recognition elements provide high specificity, enabling rapid and sensitive detection of biomarkers or environmental pollutants through discernible changes in the electrochemical signal upon binding events between immobilised bioreceptors and target analytes. The integration of DNA nanotechnology, nanomaterial-based sensors, and electrochemical techniques present a promising path for point-of-care detection, applicable to both environmental monitoring and health diagnostics.

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